

DESIGN OF DISTRIBUTED HONEYPOT SYSTEM BASED ON INTRUSION TRACKING

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A distributed system is proposed which remedy the existing deficiency in the centralised control system to improve network security and presents the experimental results which successfully improves the performance of the safety defence systems.

Honeypot technology has been widely used to overcome the limitations of firewall technology, many intrusion detection systems, intrusion prevention systems, which detected several attacks but couldnot detect new attacks. This paper discusses the honeypot technology according to the existed shortage in the honeypot system and proposes a distributed system which remedy the existing deficiency in the centralised control system to improve network security and presents the experimental results which successfully improves the performance of the safety defence systems.

Nowdays firewall technology in the field of the network security has been used widely, however, facing to various means of attacks, the vulnerability and limitations of firewall technology are more obvious. The paper discusses the honey pot technology in the field of the network security technology. According to the existed shortage of honeypot system, the distributed honey pot intrusion system based on intrusion tracking was proposed. The system uses distributed deployment.It expands the network area, and uses the package marking technology to identify sources of real attacks. The existed network is protected better.

To detect the blackhat society it is necessary to keep up-to-date with the hackers innovations. Various security defense systems were introduced for the improvement of network security but couldnot detect attacks inside an organisation network. Also, inspite of the advances in technology, it doesnot recognizes the new attacks.

It handles the messeges, and performs sample matching. Another function of control center is it generates the alarm, and identifies intrusion.. Also attack source can be find out by tracking techniques. .

The original intention of honeypots is to allow hackers to collect evidence while hiding the real server address, so a qualified honeynet is required to have these functions that to detect attacks, generate warnings, record, deceive, and assist in investigations. Another feature is done by the administrator to sue intruders based on evidence collected by Honeynet when necessary (Yang and Mi 2011;Du et al. 2013). The solution implements the entire solution on a Content courtesy of Springer Nature, terms of use apply.

Although security systems like intrusion detection systems (IDS), firewalls, intrusion prevention systems (IPS) have been existent since many years to enhance the security of networks; various issues were raised with regards to detection of new attacks. A common tool to augment existing attack detection mechanisms within networks is honeypot and by using such systems, new attacks could be uncovered, assault patterns might be revealed, and the precise thought processes of the intruder could be studied.

The Internet is a network of networks. It is based on the concept of packet switching. Though the services offered by Internet are extensively used from a layman to multi-millionaire it also has its own defects. Many attacks on Internet are being identified and reported. Some of the common types of network attacks are saves dropping, data modification, identity spoofing, password-based attacks and denial of service attacks. To overcome all these types of attacks an organisation usually installs an intrusion detection system to protect the confidential data exchanged over its network. The local network is then connected to the Internet thereby availing the employees to be online on the fly. Information security has three main objectives namely 1. Data confidentiality 2.Data integrity 3. Data availability. Data confidentiality ensures that the secure data can be accessed only by authorized persons. Data integrity allows secure modification of data. Data availability ensures that the data is available

readily to authorized persons. Small scale industries often do not prefer on intrusion detection systems due to its installation and maintenance costs.

Attacks on the internet keep on increasing and it causes harm to our security system. In order to minimize this threat, it is necessary to have a security system that has the ability to detect zero-day attacks and block them. “Honeytrap is the proactive defense technology, in which resources placed in a network with the aim to observe and capture new attacks”. This paper proposes a honeytrap-based model for intrusion detection system (IDS) to obtain the best useful data about the attacker. The ability and the limitations of Honeytraps were tested and aspects of it that need to be improved were identified. In the future, we aim to use this trend for early prevention so that pre-emptive action is taken before any unexpected harm to our security system.

A distributed neural network learning algorithm that can perform detection at a high detection speed and low false alarm rate and compares it with ARTMAP and BP neural network on a standard intrusion detection benchmark.

We explained honeytrap systems in detail, and implemented low interaction, middle interaction and high interaction honeytraps at laboratory. Our goal was to understand their strategy and how they are working in order to lure intruders towards the system. We discovered their security flaws in order to help researchers and organizations. Several companies are using honeytrap systems to protect the whole organization's network security, and researchers are making academic experiments on them at schools. As we all know network security is very significant for all computer systems because any unprotected machine in a network can be compromised in any minute. One may lose all the secret and important data of a company, which can be a great loss, and it is also very dangerous that someone else knows your important personal information. Thus, we tried to find answers for honeytraps' security using all interaction honeytraps possible. Our main goal for our thesis was to see if honeytraps are easy to hack and check if they are really isolated from other networks like a organization's network. When a honeytrap is compromised, is it possible to reach other systems and compromise them too ? After the system is compromised, is it possible to track the hacker by using necessary forensic science tools ? How efficient are they ? As we stated in results and analysis part, we easily hacked all the honeytraps that we used for our thesis. Especially, low interaction honeytrap Honeyd can be hacked easily without too much effort. As we stated before, any amateur hacker can seize the

system and also can see that it is a trap system. Therefore, Honeyd is not a good honeypot as its features are not efficient to fool the hacker. As Honeyd is a daemon, it is just simulating a operating system's services. So, it is not possible to a hacker to seize other systems using Honeyd. For the intruder, it will not take time to see that the system is not real, so he will not continue compromising it. He will leave the system. For forensic part, Honeyd's log was sufficient to see the actions of the hacker. Next part was to try Nepenthes as medium interaction honeypots. The result was quite similar. Thus, we came up with this conclusion: Low interaction honeypots and medium interaction honeypots are just simulating the services of a real system, because of that it is not possible to capture significant data from intruders. They are slightly different from each other but the main idea is the same. As they are not real operating systems, it is not risky to build them. There is no need to mention about further attacks. So, we moved on to the last level. After working low interaction and medium interaction honeypots, we decided to deploy high interaction honeypots. We studied on Honeywall. Even though it is time consuming and difficult, we managed to create a structure and worked on it. Our result were more interesting than before. High interaction honeypots are not virtualizing the system. They are real systems. So, it is very risky but the captured information is important. After deploying the implementation correctly, we successfully hacked the honeynet, but not Honeywall itself. It was the result we were looking for. As we stated in this paper, honeypot systems are still very new but are a great tool to identify cyber threats. The problem nowadays is that a very good hacker will most likely be able to understand when he is attacking a honeypot. Low interaction honeypots will be able to identify mostly automated attack and will hardly be able to understand new hacker method. On the other hand, high interaction systems are here to entrap the hacker and make him give away his techniques and tools to the forensic team. The network administrator implementing this kind of honeypot should make sure that the system is completely isolated from the production network. This is the best defense if the hacker compromises the honeypot. Network security is not a path many students are taking but we see it as one of the most important topics when we speak about computing. We were curious about this subject and decided to write a thesis on that field. This work taught us a lot about the black hat and white hat community. It also gave us an idea how huge and complex the forensic work is. New threats are discovered everyday and the best way to stay protected is to always stay up to date. By doing this simple task, most attacks will not have any

effect on the system. The problem nowadays is that people using pirated version of an operating system are contributing to botnets. Their system does not support critical updates and they are more sensitive to automated attacks. Nowadays, the implementation and development of honeypots are under control by network security expert. The weakness of this system is that it is not backed up by a clear legislation. Most of the work in the future should be about improving the laws about honeypots. The current laws about honeypots in most of the countries are not clear. There is a gap between the lawyers and the IT professionals. They should learn to cooperate with each other in order to clarify the legislation and give a clear answer about the legality of this technology. A lot of work should be done in the future to improve this situation. On a technical aspect, the main difficulty is to keep up with the new attacks. These days, it is not hard to detect a honeypot system, most of the work should focus on making this technology stealthier.

This paper proposes a honeypot-based model for intrusion detection system (IDS) to obtain the best useful data about the attacker to take pre-emptive action before any unexpected harm to the security system.

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